

CK1 α -PTEN axis drives tumour suppressive autophagy

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The phosphatase PTEN governs tumour suppression predominantly through the regulation of the PI-3 Kinase pathway. A study now shows that a non-catalytic function of CK1 α outcompetes the E3 ligase NEDD4-1 to stabilize PTEN, which activates FOXO3A-dependent ATG7 expression and stimulates tumour suppressive autophagy.

Tumour suppression is a multifaceted process that guards organismal homeostasis. Cancer research has revealed tumour suppressors including the phosphatase and tensin homologue deleted on chromosome ten (PTEN). PTEN inhibits PI-3 kinase pathway signalling and releases the transcriptional activity of FOXO family factors¹. Yet, the regulatory mechanisms and the effector pathways of PTEN are not fully understood¹. Macroautophagy (hereafter referred to as autophagy) is a central process to recycle cellular components, eliminate damaged organelles and provide cells with building blocks². Tumour suppressors and oncogenes exhibit multiple means to activate, inhibit or reprogram autophagy. In this issue, Cai *et al.* decipher the tumour suppressive activity of Casein kinase 1 α (CK1 α) in non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), showing that CK1 α elicits PTEN-dependent autophagy through a previously unknown AKT/FOXO3A/ATG7 axis³.

The analysis of CK1 α tumour suppressive activity in NSCLC by Cai *et al.* stemmed from the observation that the activation status of autophagy was associated with changes in the abundance of this kinase in cell lines. Conversely, manipulation of CK1 α altered autophagic flux³. This relationship suggested the existence of a biological activity governed by a reciprocal positive feedback regulation between CK1 α and autophagy. Interestingly, the alteration of autophagy upon the genetic inhibition of CK1 α was associated with accelerated growth and tumourigenicity both *in vitro* and *in vivo* in NSCLC cells. Significantly longer median survival time of NSCLC patients with high CK1 α expression provided further support for its activity in cancer³. A previous report proposed a tumour suppressive role for CK1 α in tumours, showing that this kinase suppresses melanoma growth through regulation of β -Catenin pathway⁴. However, CK1 α , as many other cancer-related genes, appears to exert tumour-type or oncogene-specific opposing activities. A study contrasting with the findings by Cai *et al.* focused on the control of mutant RAS-driven autophagy (specifically in colorectal and bladder cancers), which is counteracted by CK1 α

expression, hence supporting oncogenicity⁵ (**Figure 1**). These results are in line with the correlation of CK1 α expression with poor survival in colorectal cancer⁶.

Through immunoprecipitation coupled with mass spectrometry, Cai *et al.* identified PTEN as an interacting partner of CK1 α . They showed that the kinase binds to the C-terminal tail of PTEN and thus competitively abrogates the binding of PTEN with its E3-ligase, NEDD4-1. Impaired interaction between PTEN and NEDD4-1 reduced the poly-ubiquitylation of the tumour suppressor, prolonged its half-life and augmented its steady state levels³. NEDD4-1 was reported as a regulator of PTEN favouring its mono and poly-ubiquitylation and affecting its nucleocytoplasmic shuttling and stability, respectively^{7,8}. Although these results were initially debated⁹, the study by Cai *et al.*³ together with others shed light on the molecular complexity that might determine that activity of NEDD4-1 towards PTEN. This mode of regulation discovered by Cai *et al.* is of particular importance, as, unlike other tumour suppressors, dosage is a key determinant of PTEN activity. Subtle changes in PTEN expression have profound consequences in cancer biology¹⁰, and thus molecular alterations beyond genomic aberrations are likely to play a role in cancer¹.

Cai *et al.* showed that the regulation of PTEN was essential for the tumour suppressive activity of CK1 α , given that expression of the kinase in PTEN deficient NSCLC cells was inconsequential for tumour cell growth and unable to elicit the activation of autophagy. As a confirmatory demonstration, re-expression of PTEN rendered these cells sensitive to the activity of CK1 α . This result was further validated in clinical samples, where the prognostic significance of CK1 α was observed only in patients harbouring tumours with detectable PTEN³. As such, experimental data points to a strong context-dependent activity of CK1 α in cancer. It is noteworthy that major cancer-related genes (mutant RAS and PTEN) are ascribed to opposing activities of the kinase. Mutant RAS drives the upregulation of CK1 α through mechanistic target of rapamycin complex 1 (mTORC1)-dependent translation, which in turn inhibits autophagic flux⁵. In contrast,

the expression of PTEN is required for CK1 α to exert its pro-autophagic tumour suppressive function in lung cancers³. Beyond the layer of complexity involving driver oncogenic cues, tissue of origin and microenvironment may play a role, given that PTEN expressing NSCLC cells harbouring mutations in RAS (A549) retain the tumour suppressive activity of CK1 α ³.

Strikingly, Cai *et al.* demonstrated that the effect of CK1 α on PTEN stability did not require its catalytic activity³. Two independent kinase-dead mutants of CK1 α recapitulated the induction of autophagy and consequent suppression of NSCLC cell growth elicited by the *wildtype* form, unlike the catalytic inhibitor D4476³. A majority of studies regarding the biological effects of CK1 α base the effects on its kinase activity. Therefore, the results presented in NSCLC cells argue in favour of a scaffold function of CK1 α , potentially related to its capacity to interfere with protein-protein interactions, as it is the case for NEDD4-1 and PTEN³.

In order to decipher the mechanism underlying PTEN-dependent activation of autophagy by CK1 α , Cai *et al.* measured the phosphorylation status of AKT and its downstream effector FOXO3A. Elevation of PTEN levels by CK1 α suppressed AKT-driven serine 253 phosphorylation of FOXO3A, thus leading to the activation of the transcription factor. Moreover, CK1 α expression correlated negatively with AKT phosphorylation and positively with FOXO3A activation exclusively in NSCLC specimens with detectable PTEN levels³. Interestingly, FOXO3A is also a target of CK1 α in RAS mutant cancers⁵, albeit with opposing outcomes and distinct molecular mechanisms. CK1 α phosphorylated FOXO3A on serine 318/320 in cells expressing oncogenic RAS, after AKT primed the transcription factor on serine 315, to promote its nuclear exclusion and the inhibition of its transcriptional activity⁵. FOXO3A is a positive regulator of autophagy¹¹ and coordinates the expression of autophagy-related proteins. In the context of the PI-3 Kinase pathway, FOXO3A plays a complementary role to mTORC1, whose inhibition relieves the inhibitory phosphorylation of ULK1 and favours the activation of autophagy². Interestingly, Cai *et al.* uncovered an additional autophagy gene as a target of FOXO3A, the ubiquitin-like modifier-

activating enzyme ATG7. This autophagy gene was robustly upregulated upon CK1 α expression in PTEN positive NSCLC cells, whereas depletion of FOXO3A hampered this effect. Similarly, expression of a FOXO3A serine 253 (S253A) mutant rendered the expression of ATG7 insensitive to CK1 α . The FOXO3A-ATG7 axis is thus instrumental to the function of CK1 α . Expression of FOXO3A or ATG7 attenuated the tumour suppressive activity of ectopic CK1 α , whereas silencing the transcription factor or the autophagy gene prevented the increase in tumour cell growth elicited by CK1 α silencing. This pathway was also operative in patients in the presence of PTEN³.

Genetic manipulation of ATG7 has served as an excellent tool to investigate the contribution of autophagy to cancer initiation, as ATG7 depletion blunts tumourigenesis and results in the formation of benign oncocytomas¹². These results reinforce the complex nature of autophagy in cancer². Exacerbation of autophagy through ATG7 ectopic expression is tumour suppressive. However, ablating the autophagic process hampers transformation, malignancy and cancer aggressiveness². It is tempting to speculate that cancer cells require basal autophagic levels for essential cellular functions, whereas perturbations in the process (both exacerbation and ablation) are detrimental for the survival of cancer cells. As small molecules inhibiting autophagic flux have been proposed for cancer treatment, it is of the utmost importance that we expand our view of the determinants of the cellular outcome of autophagic alterations in cancer.

PTEN is a stereotypic tumour suppressor, yet its activity goes beyond the tumourigenic process. An elevated genetic dose of this tumour suppressor has been exploited as an experimental tool to decipher the feasibility of living with an enhanced anti-tumour status, through the use of bacterial artificial chromosome (BAC)-based transgenesis in mice. As predicted, mice with endogenously regulated extra copies of *Pten* (super-Pten mice) are cancer protected^{13,14}. This mouse model also revealed additional physiological activities of the tumour suppressor. Super-Pten mice exhibited healthy aging, reduced size and elevated metabolic rate, associated in part with the activation of brown adipose tissue function. The study by Cai *et al.* provides a

robust link between the elevation of PTEN and the activation of the autophagic process through FOXO3A and ATG7 regulation. Given the association of autophagy with cell fitness and aging¹⁵, it will be interesting to ascertain how the PI-3 Kinase pathway may influence these components to regulate cell fitness, healthy aging and lifespan.

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FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1. Schematic representation of Casein Kinase 1 alpha regulation of FOXO3A-driven tumour suppression. Mutated oncogenic RAS and intact PTEN are determinants of the molecular activity of CK1 α . In non-small cell lung cancer, CK1 α exerts a kinase-independent tumour suppressive activity through the inhibition of NEDD4-1-mediated PTEN degradation. Exacerbated PTEN levels suppress serine 253 phosphorylation of FOXO3A downstream of AKT, thus unleashing the activity of the transcription factor. FOXO3A induces ATG7 to elicit tumour suppressive autophagy. Conversely, activation of autophagy results in CK1 α accumulation through unknown mechanisms. In RAS mutant colorectal and bladder cancers, activation of this oncogene elicits mTORC1-mediated CK1 α protein expression, which inhibits FOXO3A through phosphorylation of serine 318/321. Inactivation of FOXO3A dampens the expression of pro-autophagic genes and attenuates the autophagic response elicited by mutant RAS. CK1 α^* depicts a function of the kinase that does not require catalytic activity.